

CERTIFICATE

OF APRECIATION

SHARQ FALSAFASI

Olimjonova Gulnoza No'monjon qizi

Teaching English by basing on pedagogical technologies.

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANDI

